

The Kutta-Joukowski Theorem and Lift Generation - A Review

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ABSTRACT

The Kutta-Joukowski theorem is a fundamental theorem of aerodynamics. The name comes from the German scientist Martin Wilhelm Kutta and the Russian scientist Nikolai Joukowski, in the early 1920s. The theorem says that the lift generated by a cylinder is proportional to the cylinder's speed through fluid, the fluid density and the circulation. In the field of steady aerodynamics theory, a fundamental role is played by the Kutta–Joukowski theorem, which relates the lift generated by an airfoil to its relative speed with respect to the fluid, the density of the fluid, and the circulation around the airfoil. Circulation is defined as the line integral, around a closed loop involving the cylinder or airfoil, of the velocity component tangent to the loop. The magnitude and direction of the fluid's velocity varies along the path.

INTRODUCTION

The importance of this theorem ⁽¹⁾ lies in its applicability in the design of effective airfoils, such as wings and propellers. When aerodynamic bodies like wings move through a fluid air, the theorem can calculate the lift generated. However it works under some assumptions such as: the flow is without internal friction, the flow is incompressible and two-dimensional. In descriptions of the theorem ⁽¹⁾ the airfoil is generally considered to be a circular cylinder or some Joukowski airfoil.

Figure 1- "Lift on rotating cylinders"- source: NASA Glenn Research Center

Before discussing the Joukowski transformation, it is necessary to present the basis that allows the direct analytical treatment used to calculate the lift of airfoils. The circulation represented by the letter Γ , can be defined as the intensity of rotation of the fluid acting on the body. Circulation⁽²⁾ is the integral of velocity around a closed loop, while Kutta's condition stipulates that flow exits tangentially at the trailing edge of an airfoil. It is defined as the line integral of the tangential velocity in a fixed closed curve in the flow:

$$\Gamma = \oint \vec{V} \cdot \vec{ds}, \quad (1)$$

where Γ is the circulation, \vec{V} is the velocity vector of any particle in the flow and \vec{ds} is an infinitesimal length of the streamline where the particle moves. In 1906, Joukowski⁽¹⁾ showed that the lift on a cylinder in a plane-parallel flow was due to the circulation of velocity in a closed contour containing the cylinder. This formulation⁽²⁾ is known as the Kutta-Joukowski Theorem:

$$\vec{L} = \rho \Gamma \vec{V}, \quad (2)$$

where \vec{L} is the reaction on the y axis, ρ is the density of the fluid in flow, \vec{V} is the velocity of the fluid and Γ is the circulation, the magnitude of which will be different for each geometry or configuration of the body, generating greater or lesser lift. Although the result given by equation (1) was obtained from a circular cylinder, it applies in general to cylindrical bodies of arbitrary cross-section. For example, consider an incompressible flow over a section of a profile, as shown in Figure 2. Let curve A be any curve in the flow around the profile. The lift per unit of the section in the profile will be given by the Kutta-Joukowski theorem, as shown in equation (1):

$$\Gamma = \oint_A \vec{V} \cdot \vec{ds} \quad (3)$$

DETAILED PROCESS OF THE DERIVATION OF KUTTA-JOUKOWSKI THEOREM

Detailed⁽³⁾ sequence for these derivation: 1. When an airfoil is exposed to an oncoming uniform fluid flow, it creates a flow around the airfoil. 2. To analyze the flow effectively, you must fix a closed path that completely borders the airfoil shape. 3. According to the theorem, the line integral of any analytical function over a simple closed curve is zero. 4. The presence of circulating flow around the airfoil induces an upward force on the body. This effect is sometimes referred to as the "Kutta-Joukowski lift". 5. After evaluating the forces around the airfoil these results are combined into a consolidated mathematical relationship, which is Kutta Joukowski's theorem.

Figure 2 Circulation around the profile

This result highlights the importance of the concept of circulation previously defined. The Kutta-Joukowski theorem⁽³⁾ states that the lift on a two-dimensional body is directly proportional to the circulation around the body. The general derivation of equation of Kutta for bodies of arbitrary cross-section can be performed using the method of variables complex. Arbitrary functions of complex variables can be shown to be general solutions of Laplace's equation, which in turn governs incompressible potential flow. Therefore, more advanced treatments of such flows use the mathematics of complex variables as a tool important. It is known that the lift flow over a circular cylinder was synthesized by the superposition of a uniform flow, a doublet, and a vortex. Remembering that the 3 elementary flows are irrotational at all points, except at the vortex, which has infinite vorticity at the origin. Therefore, the lift flow over a cylinder, as shown in Figure 1, is irrotational at all points except the origin. If circulation is taken around any curve not close to the origin, it is obtained as the result that $\Gamma = 0$. Only when it is chosen a curve that approaches⁽³⁾ the origin, where $\nabla \times \vec{V}$ is infinite, produces a finite Γ , equal to the vortex intensity. How it is known, out-of-profile flow is non-rotational and circulation around closed curves not close to the profile is consequently zero. On the other hand, it is known that the flow over the profile is synthesized by vortices distributed on the surface or inside the profile. These vortices have the usual singularities in $\nabla \times \vec{V}$ and, therefore, if a curve is chosen close to the profile, it produces a finite value of Γ , equal to the sum of the vortex intensities distributed on or within the profile. The important point here is that, in the Kutta-Joukowski theorem, the value used in the equation general must be evaluated around a closed curve that surrounds the body. It can be arbitrary, but it must contain the body. The approach discussed above – the definition of circulation and the use of Kutta's equation to obtain lift – is the essence of lift circulation theory in aerodynamics. Its development in the early 20th century created a breakthrough in aerodynamics. Lift circulation⁽⁴⁾ theory is an alternative way of thinking about the generation of lift on an aerodynamic body. The Kutta-Joukowski theorem is simply an alternative way of expressing the consequences of pressure distribution over a surface, it is a mathematical expression consistent with the special tools that have been developed for the analysis of non-viscous and incompressible flows. In fact, remembering that Kutta's equation was derived by integrating the pressure distribution over the surface. Therefore, it is not entirely accurate to say that circulation "causes" elevation. Instead, it is "caused" by the net imbalance of surface pressure distribution, and circulation is simply a quantity determined by the pressures themselves. The relationship between the distribution of surface pressures (which produce elevation L') and circulation is given by equation (1). However, in incompressible potential flow theory, it is generally much easier to determine the circulation around the body than to calculate the detailed surface pressure distribution. There in lies the power of upward circulation theory. Consequently, the theoretical analysis of lift in two-dimensional bodies in invisible and incompressible flows focuses on the calculation of circulation over the body. So the question arises:
How can it be calculated the circulation of a given body in a non-viscous and incompressible flow?

Figure 3- Effect of different values of circulation on the potential flow over a given angle of attack. Points 1 and 2 are stagnation points

KUTTA CONDITION

Flow over a circular cylinder was analyzed at the beginning of the article, where it has been observed an infinite number of possible solutions^(3,4,5) for a potential flow, corresponding to the infinite selection of Γ . For example, if there are three different flows over a cylinder, this corresponds to three different values of Γ . The same situation applies to potential flow over a profile; for a given profile at a given angle of attack, there is an infinite number of valid theoretical solutions, corresponding to a selected infinite Γ . For example, different flows over the same profile at the same angle of attack may have different values of Γ in Figure^(4,5) 3. At first, this may seem like a dilemma. It is known from experience that for a given profile at a given angle of attack produces a single lift value. So, although there are an infinite number of possible potential flow solutions, it is naturally known how to choose a specific solution. Clearly, the analysis^(3,4,5) discussed so far is not complete therefore an additional condition that defines Γ for a given profile as a given angle of attack α is required. To try to find this condition, it is opportune to examine some experimental results for the development of a flow field around a profile that is moving from an initial state of rest. Figure 4 shows a series of classic photographs of a flow over a profile⁽⁴⁾ taken from the book by Prandtl and Tiejens. In Figure^(4,5) 4(a), the flow has just begun and the flow pattern begins to develop around the profile. In these early moments of development, the flow attempts to coil around the shape of the trailing edge from the lower surface to the upper surface. However, more detailed considerations of a non-viscous and incompressible flow show a theoretical result that the velocity becomes infinitely large at a sharp corner, hence the type of flow drawn in figure 4(a), which is naturally not well tolerated.

Figure 4 – Visualization^(4,5) of the impulsive start flow around an airfoil: (a) early transient; (b) steady state; (c) The final steady flow

During the transient period, the flow rotates around the trailing edge. After reaching steady state, the flow leaves the trailing edge smoothly and the Kutta condition is satisfied. Instead, as the actual flow over the profile develops, the stagnation point on the upper surface, point 2 in Figure 3, moves toward the trailing edge. Figure 4 (b) shows this intermediate stage. Finally, after the initial transition process ends, the steady flow shown in Figure 4 (c) is achieved. This photograph shows that the flow gently detaches from the bottom surface and the top surface of the profile at the trailing edge. This flow pattern is drawn to the right of Figure 3 and represents the type of pattern expected from a constant flow over a profile. Reflecting^(4,5) on Figures 3 and 4, it is again emphasized that setting the flow constant over a given profile at a given angle the leading edge naturally adopts the particular circulation value (in Figure 3) that results in smooth spillage of the flow at the trailing edge. This observation was made and used for the first time in theoretical analysis by Wilhelm Kutta in 1902. Thus, it became known as Kutta's Condition.

To apply Kutta's condition⁽⁴⁾ in a theoretical analysis, it is necessary to be more precise about the nature of the flow at the trailing edge. The trailing edge can have a finite angle as shown in Figures 3 and 4 and as drawn on the left of Figure 5, or it can be curved as shown on the right of Figure 5. First, it is considered the trailing edge has a finite angle. The velocities along the upper surface and the lower surface are represented as \vec{V}_1 and \vec{V}_2 and they are parallel to the upper surface at point a and they are parallel to the lower surface at point a for a finite trailing edge angle. If these velocities are finite at point a , then they must have different directions at the same point, as shown on the left of Figure 5. However, this is not physically possible, and the only possibility for both is to assume the value 0 at point a . That is, for the finite trailing edge, point a is a stagnation point, where $V_1=V_2=0$. In contrast to the curved edge shown on the right of Figure^(4,5) 5, the velocities have the same direction at point a and Bernoulli's equation can be applied.

Figure 5 - Different possible shapes of the trailing edge and their relationship to Kutta's condition

Therefore, for the curved leading edge, it is observed that the velocities leaving the upper surface and the lower surface of the profile at the trailing edge are finite and equal in magnitude and direction. For a given profile^(4,5) at a given angle of attack, the value of Γ around the profile is such that the flow separates smoothly from the trailing edge. If the trailing edge angle is finite, then the trailing edge is a stagnation point. If the trailing edge is curved, then the detachment velocities at the upper surface and at the lower surface of the trailing edge are finite and equal in magnitude and direction. Considering again the possibility of simulating^(4,5) the profile with vortex sheets placed on the surface or curvature line denoting the velocities by \vec{V}_1 and \vec{V}_2 and the point a corresponding to the trailing edge. In this situation, if the trailing edge has a finite angle, the velocities \vec{V}_1 and \vec{V}_2 would present two different directions at the same point, which is physically impossible. Therefore, it is necessary that the velocities V_1 and V_2 are zero in a , that is, the trailing edge constitutes a stagnation point if it presents a finite angle. In the case of a curved edge, the velocities \vec{V}_1 and \vec{V}_2 have the same direction at point a and therefore, both can have finite values. However, it must be noted that the pressure at that point must present a single value. Using Bernoulli's equation:

$$p_a + \frac{1}{2}\rho V_1^2 = p_a + \frac{1}{2}\rho V_2^2, \quad (4)$$

that is

$$V_1 = V_2$$

Thus, for a curved edge, the velocities on the upper and lower sides must have a finite value, being equal in magnitude and direction. Thus, Kutta's condition can be summarized as follows: For an airfoil with a given angle of attack, the value of the circulation Γ around the airfoil must be such that the flow is smooth at the trailing edge that has a finite angle, then this point will be a stagnation point. If the edge is curved, then the velocities are finite and equal in magnitude and direction. The magnitude of the vortex⁽⁵⁾ sheet is variable along the sheet and is denoted by $\gamma(s)$. The surface intensity of vortex vortices, as a function of the Kutta condition, is given by

$$\gamma(TE) = \gamma(a) = V_1 - V_2, \quad (5)$$

where TE corresponds to the abbreviation for trailing edge. It is observed that both in the case of a trailing edge with a finite angle and for a curved edge, $V_1 = V_2$ or $\gamma(TE) = 0$. In this way, the Kutta condition can be expressed in terms of the intensity of the vortex surface as

$$\gamma(TE) = 0 \quad (6)$$

IS IT POSSIBLE TO LIFT WITHOUT FRICTION?

It has already been emphasized that the resulting aerodynamic force^(3,4,5) on a body immersed in a flow is due to the integrated net effect of pressure and shear stresses distributed over the surface of the body. Furthermore it has been noticed that the elevation in a profile is mainly due to the pressure distribution on the surface and that shear stresses have no virtual elevation effect. To make this fact clearer it is opportune to observe the shapes of the profiles in figures 3 and 4, for example and notice that for these profiles the direction of normal pressure is essentially in the vertical direction, that is, the lift direction. In contrast, shear stresses act tangentially to the surface, and for

these profiles the direction of these tangential shear stresses is mainly in the horizontal direction, that is, in the direction of drag. Therefore, pressure is the dominant factor in generating uplift and shear stresses are insignificant in the uplift effect. It is for this reason that the elevation in a profile below collapse can be accurately predicted by non-viscous fluid theories. However in a perfectly non-viscous world, a profile would not produce lift. In fact, the presence of friction is a very important reason why lift is achieved. This sounds a little strange, even contradictory, to previous discussion. What's going on here? The answer is that in real life, the natural way of ensuring that the flow is released smoothly at the leading edge, that is, the mechanism that nature uses to choose the flow shown in Figure 4 (c) is that the viscous layer boundary remains attached to the surface up to the leading edge. Naturally, Kutta's condition is imposed through friction. If there were no (frictionless) boundary layer, there would be no real-life physical mechanism for achieving the Kutta condition. So it can be said that⁽⁶⁾ without friction there would be no lift.

KELVIN'S INITIAL VORTEX AND CIRCULATION THEOREM

Specifically, Kutta's condition^(5,6) states that the circulation around a profile is exactly the right value that ensures the flow separates smoothly from the trailing edge. Kelvin's theorem helps explain the generation of circulation around a profile. At this point the question arises: How does nature generate this circulation?

Figure 6 – About Kelvin's theorem

Does it come from nowhere or is the circulation somehow conserved throughout the flow field? This issue will be looked more closely considering an arbitrary, non-viscous and incompressible flow like the one drawn in Figure 6. It is supposed^(5,67) that the forces \vec{f} on the entire body are zero. It is chosen an arbitrary curve C_1 and the flow elements that are on this curve at a given instant t_1 are identified. Furthermore, by definition, the circulation around the curve C_1 is

$$\Gamma_1 = - \oint_{C_1} \vec{V} \cdot d\vec{s} \quad (7)$$

Now let's let these specific fluid elements move freely. Over time t_2 , these same elements of the fluid form a new curve C_2 , around which the new circulation is

$$\Gamma_2 = - \oint_{C_2} \vec{V} \cdot d\vec{s} \quad (8)$$

For the conditions indicated above

$$\Gamma_1 = \Gamma_2 \quad \text{and} \quad \Gamma_3 = \Gamma_4$$

In fact, because a group of specific fluid elements are being tracked, it can be established that the circulation around a closed curve formed by a group of contiguous fluid elements remains constant as the fluid elements move along the flow. Remembering that it is a derivative that provides a change of a given fluid element in a time interval. Therefore a simple mathematical statement from the above discussion is that the time interval of circulation change around a closed curve consists of the fluid elements themselves being equal to zero. That is

$$\frac{d\Gamma}{dt} = 0 \quad (9)$$

The preceding equation is called the Kelvin Circulation Theorem. An interesting consequence of the Kelvin circulation theorem⁽⁸⁾ proves that a flow surface that is a vortex sheet at some instant in time remains a vortex sheet for all time.

DERIVATION OF KUTTA-JOUKOWSKI THEOREM

Consider the force^(8,9) exerted on each unit of length of a cylinder of arbitrary cross section.

$$\vec{F} = -\oint_C p \vec{n} \cdot \vec{ds}, \quad (10)$$

Since C represents the limit of this cylinder and p indicates the static pressure of the fluid, \vec{n} is the unit vector normal to the cylinder, while \vec{ds} corresponds to the arc element of the cross – section boundary. Now consider that ϕ is the angular displacement between the normal vector and the vertical axis. Therefore, the components of the force previously indicated are

$$F_x = -\oint_C p \sin\phi ds, F_y = \oint_C p \cos\phi ds \quad (11)$$

On the other hand, we know that a vector can be represented as a complex number. In this way, the complex form of that force^(8,9,10) is

$$F = F_x + iF_y = -\oint_C p(\sin\phi - i\cos\phi) ds \quad (12)$$

Considering the complex force conjugate with small modifications we arrive at

$$\bar{F} = -\oint_C p(\sin\phi + i\cos\phi) ds = -i\oint_C p(\cos\phi - i\sin\phi) ds = -i\oint_C p e^{-i\phi} ds \quad (13)$$

We can replace ds by dz by making the following deduction:

$$dz = dx + idy = ds(\cos\phi + i\sin\phi) = ds e^{i\phi} \Rightarrow \bar{dz} = e^{-i\phi} ds \quad (14)$$

That said, the result is

$$\bar{F} = -i\oint_C p \bar{dz} \quad (15)$$

Equation 15 requires the pressure to be explained. For this purpose, the following Bernoulli equation will be used. The mass density of the flow is ρ .

$$p = p_0 - \frac{\rho|v|^2}{2} \quad (16)$$

Hence the force \bar{F} becomes ^(9,10)

$$\bar{F} = -i\rho_0 \oint_C \bar{d}z + i \frac{\rho}{2} \oint_C |v|^2 \bar{d}z = \frac{i\rho}{2} \oint_C |v|^2 \bar{d}z \quad (17)$$

To facilitate deductions, the complex potential of the flow $w=f(z)$ will be introduced. This is related to the velocity components as $w' = v_x - iv_y = \bar{v}$, where w' denotes differentiation with respect to the complex variable z . Remembering that $v = \pm|v|e^{i\theta}$ and $v^2 \bar{d}z = |v|^2 dz$, the expression for the force is obtained.

$$\bar{F} = \frac{i\rho}{2} \oint_C w'^2(z) dz, \quad (18)$$

which is called the Blasius theorem.

Consider now that:

$$w'(z) = a_0 + \frac{a_1}{z} + \frac{a_2}{z^2} + \dots \quad (19)$$

Being that

$$a_0 = v_{x\infty} - iv_{y\infty} \quad \text{and} \quad a_1 = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \oint_C w'(z) dz \quad (20)$$

Now perform the above integration we must:

$$\oint_C w'(z) dz = \oint_C (v_x - iv_y)(dx + idy) \quad (21)$$

$$\oint_C (v_x dx + v_y dy) + i \oint_C (v_x dy - v_y dx) \quad (22)$$

$$\oint_C v ds + i \oint_C (v_x dy - v_y dx) \quad (23)$$

The first integral is recognized as the circulation denoted by Γ . The second integral can be evaluated after some manipulation ^(8,9,10)

$$\oint_C (v_x dy - v_y dx) = \oint_C \left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} dy + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} dx \right) = \oint_C d\psi = 0 \quad (24)$$

Here ψ is the stream function. Making some rearrangements and considerations, we find that

$$a_1 = \frac{\Gamma}{2\pi i} \quad (25)$$

By taking the square of the series

$$w'^2(z) = a_0^2 + \frac{a_0\Gamma}{\pi iz} + \dots \quad (26)$$

Returning with the value of the Blasius equation and carrying out the integration using the residue theorem we arrive at the general formula given by the equation ^(8,9) 27

$$\bar{F} = \frac{i\rho}{2} \left[2\pi i \frac{a_0\Gamma}{\pi i} \right] = i\rho a_0\Gamma = i\rho\Gamma(v_{x\infty} - iv_{y\infty}) = \rho\Gamma v_{y\infty} + i\rho\Gamma v_{x\infty} = F_x - iF_y, \quad (27)$$

where

$$F_x = \rho\Gamma v_{y\infty}, F_y = -\rho\Gamma v_{x\infty} \quad (28)$$

Finally, it is possible to write the final expression from Kutta-Joukowski theorem

$$\rho V \Gamma \quad (29)$$

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

These considerations were based on content extracted from references 13 and 14, which indicate that the Kutta-Joukowski theorem is found wherever fluid mechanics plays a role. When it comes to an airfoil, to obtain greater lift and less drag, experts usually use the Kutta-Joukowski theorem. To understand the theorem it is necessary to decompose its integrated aspects, especially the concept of support. Lift theory, established by Kutta and Joukowski, implies that the amount of lift depends mainly on the circulation around the airfoil. The Kutta-Joukowski theorem has improved our understanding of how lift is generated, allowing us to create better, faster, more efficient aircraft that produce lift. When flow over the profile begins, the high-velocity gradient in the shape of the trailing edge results in the formation of a region of intense velocity, forming the initial vortex. This initial vortex is associated with a counterclockwise circulation. Therefore, as an equal and opposite reaction, a clockwise circulation is generated around the profile.

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